

MONUMENTS

FOR THE
SELF-REBUILT
BY PABLO ANGEL LUGO

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Deconstruction is a process that is not only part of social or economic systems. Thinking about how we rebuild ourselves is part of the constant process of changing, considering ourselves as a continuity of change. Some people think about this change in religious terms: for Taoists, it is something that moves everything, it is the Ying-Yang, a system of continuous movement created by the opposition of contraries, which is not far from Hegel's dialectic.

Thinking about deconstruction as a constant movement —social and personal— we can think about it in different ways. How does jail change a person who has been imprisoned for the wrong reason? How can we talk to a woman who has been raped? What about a kid who was abused by a priest? Or those elders that have been abandoned by the government that they founded? Or that teenager who has been bullied for ages and tried to kill herself?

These sculptures are monuments to tell all those people that there are different ways to heal themselves. Sculptures made by rubbish, remains from society trying to get up in one piece. But that is not possible, because when something is broken there is no way that it can come back the same, and once again, Taoism and Hegel touch, the river is the same, but at the same time it is not.

There are different ways to rebuild yourself, whether by need, by survival, by desire or by force. Kintsugi is the name that Japanese people have given to the art of rebuilding a broken object. To get that object back to use, they glue its remains with gold. A beautiful metaphor: everyone needs something valuable to repair themselves. And for that, they deserve monuments. There is not only one way to rebuild yourself, and there are thousands of paths to do it. For that reason, each monument has to be different. And not all the tracks have the same opportunities or privileges to help us to rise in the best way possible.

No matter what, people that have rebuilt themselves deserve a monument. So there you have it. Choose yours.

Monument to the self-rebuild I
(Ethical non monogamous)

Plaster & wood

27 x 19 x 24 cm

2019

Monument to the self-rebuild II

Plaster & wood

16 x 14 x 12 cm

2019

Monument to the self-rebuild III
(Vegans)

Plaster & resin

11.5 x 8.5 x 11 cm

2019

Monument to the self-rebuild IV
(No-binary)

Plaster

12 x 9 x 16.5 cm

2019

Monument to the self-rebuild V

Plaster

14 x 9 x 16 cm

2019

Monument to the self-rebuild VI
(Ugly)

Plaster

11.5 x 9 x 17 cm

2019

Monument to the self-rebuild VII
(Refugees)

Plaster

16 x 14 x 12 cm

2019

Monument to the self-rebuild VIII
(Raped)

Plaster

11.5 x 15 x 17 cm

2019

Monument to the self-rebuild IX
(Pee themselves)

Plaster

14 x 12 x 24 cm

2019

Monument to the self-rebuild X
(Machismo victims)

Plaster

14.5 x 12.5 x 23 cm

2019

Monument to the self-rebuild XI
(Abused children)

Plaster

14.5 x 12.5 x 29.5 cm

2019

Monument to the self-rebuild XII
(Broken hearted)

Gold leaves / plaster

8 x 5.5 x 9.5 cm

2019

Monument to the self-rebuild XIII

Gold leaves / plaster

14 x 15 x 16 cm

2019

Monument to the self-rebuild XIV

Gold leaves / plaster

14 x 13 x 16.5 cm

2019

Monument to the self-rebuild XV
(Emotionally broken)

Gold leaves / plaster & wood

13 x 10.5 x 28.5 cm

2019

Monument to the self-rebuild XVI
(Mentally ill)

Gold leaves / plaster & wood

22 x 26 x 26 cm

2019

Monument to the self-rebuild XVII
(Political prisoners)

Gold leaves / plaster

14.5 x 12 x 29 cm

2019

Monument to the self-rebuild XVIII

Gold leaves / plaster

11.5 x 9 x 39 cm

2019

PABLO ANGEL LUGO

Pablo Angel Lugo is an artist of considerable international reputation and enviable academic background, born in Mexico City. His work has taken him worldwide and been exhibited likewise.

Pablo's speciality is in public art, but his vast artistic output includes paintings, drawings, engravings, sculptures, videos, performances, illustrations, graphic designs and cinematic collaborations.

His work has been exhibited in Mexico, Cuba, USA, UK, Spain, Colombia, France, Portugal, Argentina and Indonesia amongst other countries.

He has studied in Mexico and Spain, earning a BA in Visual Arts and an MA and an MPhil in Public Art, he is currently completing his PhD in Public Art supported by a scholarship from the Jumex Foundation.

He is a veteran of many courses and workshops and also teaches both in the UK and overseas in his areas of speciality. Pablo is a member of some professional associations and a founding member of the Free University Collective of Art Theory and Research, the Circular Workshop of Graphic Production, the Autonomous Gallery in the National School of Plastic Arts and of the self-managed cultural centre The Three in Valencia.

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